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Relationship Between Physicochemical Parameters and Fresh Water Snail Abundance in Bayelsa State, South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the environmental factors affecting the distribution and habitat preferences of snail intermediate hosts is crucial for the effective control and elimination of snail-borne diseases. The study is aimed at assessing the relationship between physico chemical parameters and snail distribution across six LGAs of Bayelsa State. A cross-sectional study was employed to collect fresh water snail samples from the study locations between July, 2023 –February, 2024. Snail productive water body were identified using GPS device. Snails were collected using standard procedures and were transported in a duly labeled 50 mL black plastic containers to the department of biological sciences laboratory, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State for identification. The snails were identified according to standard pictorial key. In the same localities, the physical and chemical parameters of the snail positive water were assessed using a probe device. The relationship between snail abundance and physio chemical parameters were determine by statistics. From the results, there was a positive correlation between P^H and *Onchomelania* (r=0.120), *P. maculatus*(r=0.182), *Biomphalaria spp* (r= 0.085) and a negative with *Bulinus globosus*(r=-0.039), *Lymnaea natalensis*(r=-0.100), *Melanoides* (r=-0.180) and *B. natalensis*. Temperature showed positive correlation with *Lymnaea natalensis*(r=0.096), *P. maculatus* (r=0.266) and *Onchomelania* (r= 0.171) but a negative correlation with *Bulinus globosus* (r=-0.433), *B. natalensis* (r=-0.177) and *Biomphalaria* (r= -0.026). Electrical conductivity positively correlated with *Bulinus globosus*(r=0.059), *Melanoides*(r=0.156) and *Biomphalaria*(r=0.232) but a negative correlation with *Lymnaea natalensis*(r=-0.168), *Oncomelania* (r=-0.132), *P. maculatus* (r=-0.165) and *B.natalensis* (r=-0.196). There was a positive correlation between Dissolved solvent concentration and *Bulinus globosus*(r=0.033), *Melanoides* (r=0.152), and *Biomphalaria*(r=0.308); between Dissolved Oxygen and *Lymnaea natalensis* (r=0.181), *Onchomelania* (r=0.287), *P.maculatus* (r=0.325) and *B. natalensis* (r=0.308). A positive correlation was observed between Biological Oxygen Demand and *Lymnaea natalensis* (r=0.094) and *Biomphalaria* (r=0.210).

Key words: Physico chemical parameters, fresh water snails, abundance, Bayelsa State

INTRODUCTION

Fresh water snail is distributed across varied ecosystem. They are among the most endangered groups of aquatic organisms that are most vulnerable to environmental changes. Studies show that approximately 60 species of freshwater snails are fast disappearing (Emil, & Sofía, 2012). The

rapid decline in the diversity of freshwater snails is due to a variety of human factors, either to destroys snail's natural habitat or prevent their proliferation. Destruction of wetlands and introduction of industrial and agricultural emissions have further deteriorated the ecosystems in, which the snails live (Xiao-Ting *et al.*, 2018).

Physical and chemical parameters such as temperature, precipitation, aquatic macrophyte cover, hydrography, substrate composition, pH, electrical conductivity, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), chemical oxygen demand, total nitrogen, and total phosphorus; food, competition, and predator–prey interactions are known to affect the distribution of fresh water snails (Mereta *et al.*, 2012; Gilioli *et al.*, 2017). The value of freshwater snails in the aquatic food web lies in their ecological role and maintenance of water quality (Chang, 2008).

Environmental factors had been known to influence the distribution, development and establishment of fresh water intermediate host (Gilioli *et al.*, 2017, Anne-Sofie *et al.*, 2006). Understanding the environmental factors affecting the distribution and habitat preferences of snail intermediate hosts is crucial for the effective control and elimination of snail-borne diseases. Bayelsa State has a heterogenous ecology with diverse environmental factors (Abowei, 2010), but only few studies have shown the relationship between these factors and snail abundance (Ebenezer, Eze, & Obi, 2016; Amawulu & Akpoebiere, 2022). The study is aimed at assessing the relationship between physico chemical parameters and snail distribution across six LGAs of Bayelsa State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Bayelsa State, (5° 22' – 6°45'E and 4°10' – 5°23'N) occupies the core of the lower deltaic plain of Nigeria. It is bounded by the Rivers Niger, Forcados, Ramos and Bomadi Creek and shares boundaries with Delta and Rivers States. Bayelsa State occupies a land area of 21,110 km² and an estimated population of 1,121,693 according to the 2006 population census. Majority of the land area is covered by water with low land, part almost below the sea level. The maze of meandering creeks and swamps crisscross the low-lying plains of the Niger Delta and kept most areas permanently water-logged. This provides a conducive environment for the breeding of fresh water snails. The sampling locations comprises of 26 communities across seven LGAs. The study area has been extensively discussed (Ebenezer, Eze, & Obi, 2016; Amawulu, & Assumpta, 2021; Amawulu & Akpoebiere, 2022).

Malacological Survey and snail identification

A cross-sectional study was employed to collect fresh water snail samples from the study locations between July, 2023 –February, 2024. Snail microhabitats were identified, and the coordinates were taken using GPS device. Microhabitats were mapped and at each selected site, snails were collected using a scoop net. Microhabitats scoop was; gutters and drainages, excavations, water pools, rivers and streams. Collected snails from each site were transported in a duly labeled 50 mL black plastic containers to the department of biological sciences laboratory, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The snails were identified according to standard pictorial key in WHO (2013).

Physicochemical analysis of the snail's microhabitat

The physical and chemical parameters of the snail positive water were assessed using a probe device (model: C-600). The physico chemical parameters taken were; temperature, pH, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), turbidity, and conductivity. In each of the positive water body, the probe device was totally emerged according to the manufacturer's instructions. This was repeated in all the sampling sites.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the study was subjected to statistical analysis. Data was analyzed using SPSS (VERSION 10) as a statistical tool. The frequency of the species of snails collected were analyzed by percentage while the relationship between the snails collected across LGAs were analyzed by correlation coefficient. Decision was ascertained at 0.05 level of confidence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean and standard deviation of water temperature, pH, Dissolved oxygen, Electrical Conductivity, BOD, DSC (ppm) across the study LGAs is shown in table 1. The mean and standard deviation of water temperature ranges from 27.86 ± 1.34 to 32.83 ± 1.82 . pH values varied from 7.30 ± 0.15 to 8.81 ± 0.96 . The highest P^H (8.81 ± 0.96) value was recorded in Ogbia while the lowest (7.30 ± 0.15) was recorded in Sourthern Ijaw. The mean ((\pm SD) of Dissolved oxygen (DO) varied across the different sampling locations, with the lowest DO (2.18 ± 1.03) value recorded in kolokuma-opkuma, and the highest (5.91 ± 2.26) value recorded in southern ijaw. Electrical Conductivity(us/cm) of the sampling locations ranges between 99.97 ± 1.15 in Ekeremor and 350.25 ± 243.21 in Ogbia. The lowest and the highest value of the BOD (mg/l) are 1.83 ± 0.75 and 6.79 ± 2.14 respectively. Highest value is recorded in Yenagoa while the lowest value was recorded in Kolokuma-Opokuma LGA. The mean and standard deviation of Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) across LGAs ranges from 1.83 ± 0.75 to 6.79 ± 2.14 . The lowest value (1.83 ± 0.75) was recorded in Kolokuma -Opokuma while the highest (6.79 ± 2.14) value was recorded in Yenagoa.

Table 1: Physicochemical parameters across study locations

	TEMP	SG	MV	P ^H	EC(us/cm)	DSC(ppm)	DO (mg/l)	BOD(mg/l)
SILGA	27.86 ± 1.34	1.002± 0.001	148.00 ± 65.79	7.30 ± 0.15	226.60 ± 154.81	113.40 ± 77.46	5.91 ± 2.26	3.58 ± 2.38
SAGBAMA	30.15 ± 2.72	1.003 ± 0.00	143.25 ± 26.51	8.19 ± 0.91	206.50 ± 63.05	103.25 ± 31.51	5.40 ± 3.08	2.64 ± 1.28
KOLOKUMA	28.80 ± 0.37	1.002 ± 0.00	150.00 ± 37.71	7.47 ± 0.92	278.00 ± 172.33	137.75 ± 86.13	2.18 ± 1.03	1.83 ± 0.75
EKEREMOR	32.83 ± 1.82	1.003± 0.001	118.00 ± 102.86	8.05 ± 1.15	99.97 ± 1.15	95.75 ± 64.61	2.40 ± 3.74	3.73 ± 2.38
OGBIA	31.58 ± 1.60	1.003± 0.001	5.75 ± 16.58	8.81 ± 0.96	350.25 ± 243.21	172.50± 18.10	4.46 ± 4.08	4.20 ± 1.99
YENAGOA	31.62 ± 2.37	1.003 ± 0.00	113.40 ± 77.74	8.62 ± 1.59	342.60 ± 223.18	167.60± 10.82	2.88 ± 3.87	6.79 ± 2.14

EC= ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

DSC= DISSOLVE SOLUTE CONTENT

DO= DISSOLVED OXYGEN

BOD= BIOLOGICAL OXYGEN DEMAND

P^H= HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION

TEMPT. = TEMPERATURE

SG=SPECIFIC GRAVITY

MV(ORP)=(OXIDATIVE REDUCTION POTENTIAL)

Relationship between physicochemical parameters and fresh water snail abundance

Figure 6 shows the relationship between the abundance of fresh water snail and physico-chemical. There was a positive correlation between PH and *Onchomelania* ($r=0.120$), *P. maculatus* ($r=0.182$), *Biomphalaria* spp ($r= 0.085$). PH had a negative correlation with *Bulinus globosus* ($r=-0.039$), *Lymnaea natalensis* ($r=-0.100$), *Melanoides* ($r=-0.180$) and *B. natalensis*. Temperature showed positive correlation with *Lymnaea natalensis* ($r=0.096$), *P. maculatus* ($r=0.266$) and *Onchomelania* ($r= 0.171$) but a negative correlation with *Bulinus globosus* ($r=-0.433$), *B. natalensis* ($r=-0.177$) and *Biomphalaria* ($r= -0.026$). Electrical conductivity positively correlated with *Bulinus globosus* ($r=0.059$), *Melanoides* ($r=0.156$) and *Biomphalaria* ($r=0.232$) but showed negative correlation with *Lymnaea natalensis* ($r=-0.168$), *Oncomelania* ($r=-0.132$), *P. maculatus* ($r=-0.165$) and *B. natalensis* ($r=-0.196$). There was a positive correlation between Dissolved solvent concentration and *Bulinus globosus* ($r=0.033$), *Melanoides* ($r=0.152$), and *Biomphalaria* ($r=0.308$); between Dissolved Oxygen and *Lymnaea natalensis* ($r=0.181$), *Onchomelania* ($r=0.287$), *P. maculatus* ($r=0.325$) and *B. natalensis* ($r=0.308$). A positive correlation was observed between Biological Oxygen Demand and *Lymnaea natalensis* ($r=0.094$) and *Biomphalaria* ($r=0.210$).

Table 2: Correlation coefficient showing the relationship between fresh water snail abundance and physico chemical parameters

	<i>Bulinus globosus</i>	<i>Lymnaea natalensis</i>	<i>Melanooides</i>	<i>Onchomelania</i>	<i>P. maculatus</i>	<i>B.natalensis</i>	<i>Biomphalaria</i>
Temp. °c	-0.433	0.096	-0.253	0.171	0.266	-0.177	-0.026
SG	-0.240	0.339	-0.385	0.211	0.212	-0.112	-0.112
MV	0.174	0.188	-0.379	0.222	-0.231	0.298	-0.196
PH	-0.039	-0.100	-0.180	0.120	0.182	-0.013	0.085
EC (us/cm)	0.059	-0.165	0.156	-0.132	-0.165	-0.196	0.232
DSC (ppm)	0.033	-0.196	0.152	-0.171	-0.188	-0.229	0.191
DO	-0.197	0.181	-0.061	0.287	0.325	0.308	-0.225
BOD	-0.300	0.094	-0.137	-0.268	-0.096	-0.026	0.210

DISCUSSION

Snail distribution in the present study correlated with eight physico chemical parameters. Temperature varied between 27.86 ± 1.34 and 32.83 ± 1.82 , It was highest in Ekeremor LGA and least in Southern Ijaw LGA. The Temperature falls within the tolerable limits

The pH is an important parameter that affects snail distribution. Studies (Chang 2008). have reported that increased in the pH level of water tends highlighted the possibility of an increased in the level of use alkaline from detergents in residential areas and wastewater alkaline materials in industrial areas. A pH higher than 7 but lower than 8.5 was reported elsewhere to be ideal for biological productivity, while pH lower than 4 was detrimental to water life (Abowei 2010). The mean P^H of the study location ranges from 7.30 ± 0.15 and 8.81 ± 0.96 . This value falls with the WHO permissible limits. Higher P^H value was recorded in Southern Ijaw LGA while the lowest was in Ogbia LGA. The pH range recorded in this study was similar with the reports of Oloyede, Otarigho & Morenikeji (2016). There was a positive correlation between P^H and *Onchomelania*, *P. maculatus*, *Biomphalaria spp.* and a negative correlation with *Bulinus globosus*, *Lymnaea natalensis*, *Melanoides* and *B. natalensis* This observation is consistent with Abdulkadir Maikaje.& Umar. (2013). However, the result was not statistically significant. This is an indication that pH alone may not have been responsible for the differences in the abundance of the fresh water snails. These results indicate a sufficient buffering property of the river that is adequate for aquatic (Andong et al., 2019).

The mean Dissolved Oxygen of the study locations varied between 2.88 ± 3.87 mg/l and 5.91 ± 2.26 mg/L). These levels are two-fold lower than the recommended limits of 8.3 mg/L. However, Salawu, & Odaibo,2021 recorded a lower DO range of (0.4 ppm–16.0 ppm. Southern Ijaw LGA recorded the highest mean DO value,while kolokuma recorded the least value These values fall within the desirable for freshwater snails Locations with high DO may be attributed to pollutions related to a density of floating vegetation, which are known to cause a shortage of DO. The low DO level recorded in the soe locations could be as a result of to low water quality resulting from probable increased organic decomposition activities due to the death and decay of aquatic macrophytes (Oso, & Odaibo, 2021)., Positive relationship was observed between dissolved oxygen and some freshwater snails. This observation is consistent with Oso, & Odaibo, (2021). However, a negative relationship observed between DO and *another snail has been recorded* Odongo-Aginya, et al., (2008). This is an indication that the snails showed preferences for high oxygen concentration but its abundance reduces mobility is reduced in when the n environment had lo w oxygen concentration, which may lead to impaired feeding and reproduction.

BOD measures the amount of dissolved oxygen in mg/l required by organism to stabilize the biodegradable organic matter under aerobic conditions and the oxidation of certain inorganic materials (APHA, 2012). The BOD recorded in this study ranges between 1.83 ± 0.75 in Kolokuma and 6.79 ± 2.14 in Yenagoa. These values fall within permissible level (WHO, 2008). BOD recorded in this study may be a consequence of additional organic matter introduced into the water body through run-off.

Both the Electrical conductivity and the Dissolved solvent concentration of the water bodies were highest in Ogbia (350.25 ± 243.21 ; 172.50 ± 18.10) and lowest in Ekeremor (99.97 ± 1.15 ; 95.75 ± 64.61). The permissible limit for electrical conductivity (EC) is $300 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. The result from this present study agrees with the permissible value. (Varsha, Neelam &, Kanchan,2013).

The Movement velocity was lowest in Ogbia (5.75 ± 16.58) and highest (150.00 ± 37.71) in Kolokuma. The Specific Gravity (SG) of the water body was uniform across locations and does not differ significantly from the specific gravity of water elsewhere (Ndlovu, & Demlie, 2020).

Correlationship exist between snail and snail. In this present study, *Bulinus globosus* showed weak negative correlation with *Lymnaea natalensis* *Melanoides spp* , *Onchomelania spp* , *Bulinus natalensis* *Biomphalaria spp* and *Pumata maculatus*, excluding *Lymnaea natalensis* and *Bulinus natalensis*, which showed weak positive correlation. Correlation between snail and snail has been reported elsewhere (Abdulkadir, Maikaje & Umar, 2013; Charles *et al.*, 2022). This result indicated that there is no competition among the snail species. A non-significant negative correlation recorded between the snail species and an invasive *Melanoides spp* is surprising and should stirs up some curiosity for further research. Research has shown that *Melanoides spp*

tolerate a broad spectrum of environmental conditions, colonizes disturbed habitats and out-compete and threaten the existence of native species (Oladejo *et al.*, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The correlation between fresh water snail and physico chemical parameters in six LGAs of Bayelsa State has been studied. The results showed that eight physico chemical parameters (temperature, pH, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), turbidity, conductivity, Electrical conductivity, specific gravity and the Dissolved solvent concentration correlated either positively or negatively with one or more of the snails' intermediate hosts. The correlation was significant. This is an indication that the abundance of the snail in the study LGAs was affected by physico chemical parameters. Moreso, a significant correlation between snail and snail exist, indicating that there was no competition among the snail species across the study LGAs. A non-significant negative correlation was also recorded between the snail species and an invasive *Melanoides spp.* This should stir up some curiosity for further research

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